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CONTRIBUTION OF FIDEL ALEJANDRO CASTRO RUZ IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN CUBA : A STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Education is equal power of weapon; it's only the key of developing society. Society does' not reform healthily without a healthy Education system. The education system depends on this countries' government policies, a good govt. provided the right way of growing society and as well as good social structure. Through this study, the Cuban education system gradually changes on the positive side to developed Cuban country. Fidel Castro's period in Cuba was the most developing era of this country. He implements lots of policies and strategies for the betterment of Cuban society. He mostly focuses on free education for all children and children's health. This study explores the educational development in Cuba from the revolutionary year 1959 to 2011. Objectives of this study to find out the educational thought of Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz, and to study the educational contribution of Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz in Cuba. This study based on qualitative methodology will be used Historical, Philosophical Method, collected data from different sources there are e-books reports, policies, websites, journal articles, national and international articles published on various platforms, etc. Paper discussed educational contribution during Castro's period.

Keywords: Development, Education, Philosophical, Revolution, Society, Thought.

"Were Kennedy not a millionaire illiterate and ignorant then he would understand that you can't revolt an against the peasants"

—Fidel Castro

In the early first half of the twenty century, Cuba's Education system was very poor. All people have been faced lots of problems during this time, government educational and employment policies were failed the employment process. This time government was controlled by the USA government and does not provide economic, social, and education properly. At that time "Fidel Castro" and "Che Guevara" together play a crucial role in the development of this nation and the movement was started from the city "Santa Clara". In the year of 1958, this big movement was spread in the total country of Cuba. An important year for Cuba's people, 1959 in January month established newly communist party by Fidel Castro (16th prime minister). After taking his government more than 100,000 youngsters, whose belong 10 years to 16 year aged children were recruited to teach all citizens

into all corners of Cuba. The main purpose was that how to read and write. At first, these literacy volunteers trained for a few weeks in different dimensions. After gained proper training then apply for the ground level of the societies. Because Fidel Castro knows the value of education for every people.

Cuban farmer's, working in the agricultural fields and others activities during the daytime and teaching them to how to read and write at night time. On the other hand in urban areas, military training areas or barracks were mostly converted into schools and in this way started the first step of the socialization process for the benefit of every citizen. Today, Cuba's teachers already continue the process of literacy initiative while focusing on the all-around development of children as well main principles of the "Revolution" on the basic morality, ethical, social, economically development. Teacher role's in a country are very important for the establishment of an entire system going to failure or not. The present work enhances the educational opportunities for

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Cuban peoples, the title of the study "Contribution of Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz in the educational system in Cuba" to the 21st century of Cuban educational system. There are multiple thought contributions on educational thought in that particular time as well as next generation of this nation for the development of the Cuban educational system.

Many efforts have been made in India to elementary education, it's a fundamental right of every child according to RTE Acts. Not only in Cuba, but in every part of the world a lot of efforts have been made to achieve the target goal of universal education. Achieve universal education is one of the important goals according to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). To understand the present education system and the Contribution of Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz education system in Cuba.

Objectives of the study

- a. To find out the educational thought of Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz.
- b. To find out the contribution of Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz in Education.

Method

The following study based on qualitative methodology will be used Historical, Philosophical Method. History is a meaningful and organized record of a past event. Secondary data-based paper, Researcher collected data from different sources there are e-books reports, policies, websites, journal articles, national and international articles published on various platforms, etc. That paper will give a brief description of "Contribution of Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz in the educational system in Cuba"

Who Was Fidel Castro?

13 August 1926 in Cuba near 'Baran' place, the Cuban dictator Fidel Castro was born. His revolutionary force starting a campaign against the opposite party guerrilla warfare Cuban dictator 'Fulgencio Batista' in 1958. Born a new leader for a country, Castro implemented his political thought and communist domestic policies. Under Castro mostly improvement all over the nation. In bad

condition of health of Fidel Castro officially transfer his power to his brother 'Raul Castro' in the year 2008. But still, we have seen some political influence in Cuba and abroad. Fidel Castro died at the age of 90 in 2016. "Reflections of Fidel," in 2007 his autobiography *My Life* was published. During 1959-1976 he was Prime Minister of Cuba then 1976-2008 worked as a President of Cuba.

Contemporary Castro's Education

New socialist man Castro mostly campaigning education for the promote Marxist-Leninist ideology. After 1959 he tried to sending a student to various countries majorly communist govt. based countries and which things learned from there then tried to apply for his nation. The article "Man and Socialism in Cuba" already mentions the educational policies of that period.

Castro's regime focused heavily on Education

Marti's educational thought plays a vital role in Cuban educational objectives. A shift was a theoretical concept to a humanistic concept. Scientific study also is introduced, the teacher training programme also is emerging.

1976 to 1990: A new period started

In this period foundation of socialist pedagogy was introduced for the improvement of the Cuban national educational system. Between the year 1976 and 1985 implemented the national educational system. In 1976, established "The Central Institute of Pedagogical Sciences" (ICCP) and enhance the great role in conducting Educational Sciences throughout all nation. Majorly changes in curriculum and programme, preparation of textbooks, etc.

The period 1991-2000 can be termed Struggle of ideological work:

Again attacks on Cuba by the Eastern European socialism and the Soviet Union due to historical circumstances have been changed a little bit that's why the so-called "Special Period in Peacetime". At that time ideological work was not done properly in the field of education. This period is clearly stated that satisfactory results.

The period between 2001 -2010reframe years

Mass media has grate role in this time for the development of this nation. Revolutionary change will come “University for All” concept and different kinds of round table programs create the like with international events as well as policies, then enrich the knowledge in the field of education for holistic development. Free education is provided in higher education for all. Create a different kind of professional course for undergraduate and master programmes. Linked with the foreign countries for the doctoral programme in your country. As Fidel Castro said, “we need to change everything that

should be changed” when man-educated development automatically comes and the nation will be developed. Education in Cuba has become more social function-basedand the most advanced science and technology-based in this period. According to 2011, Cuba’s total population is 11.2 million, and in nearly the past 50 years 1 million universities graduated. Children attending primary school 99.4 %, between 6 to 11 years of age. More or less Ninety-five percent of students have completed their studies in the basic level, under social inclusion, 41,000 students belonging from different types of disabilities.

(Data taken from official statistics of the Ministry of Education, Cuba)	
Before 1959	Today 2011
Active teachers were 22000, the population was 6 million.	Total population 11.2 million, 15741 teachers was done training, 258,126 teachers attended the last years of the teacher education system.
Education budget: 79.4 million pesos.	Education budget: 96 billion pesos (2010).
Illiteracy was 23.6% up to 15-year-olds.	The illiteracy rate was 0.2% up to age group over 10 years.
Three years of Average schooling. - Only 55.1% of children’s enrolled in school, between 6 to 11 years.	Average 10 years schooling – Mostly 99.7% of children are attending or have completed primary education, 6 to 11 years of age.
Three state universities were available with Limited access.	Total 65 universities for higher education and most are proper use of technology-based.
The low number of university graduates students pass out.	One million students are university graduates in the period 1960-2010.
6 teacher-training schools, with lack of various accessibly.	16 universities of Pedagogical Sciences universities are 16 number and 18 pedagogical schools for the training teachers.

Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz’s Education

Structure of the Education System

The Cuban education structure following sub-categories

- a. Pre-school education
- b. Adult Education
- c. Higher Education
- d. Special Education
- e. Technical and Vocational Education
- f. Training and Improvement of the Pedagogical Staff
- g. General, Polytechnic and Labour Education

Cuba and its Education System

17 December 2014, President Barack Obama’ stated that plan’s for the normalization of diplomatic relations between Cuba and the United State in the ease of restrictions on the economic perspective. President Barack Obama’ also said towards re-opening the embassy for this nation and allowed for travel, cultural exchange, and education. This relation enhances modern education throughout the whole world.

Some facts on Cuba’s education system

- a) Since 1961, the educational system of Cuba, has been running with help of the state nationalizing

- private institutions for all stages of education in all nations.
- b) The Cuban govt. 100% subsidized for education budget all Cuban school children can attend free in school.
 - c) According to the World Bank report 2014, Cuba has played the better education system in the level of high-level teaching faculty among the Latin American and the Caribbean.
 - d) The World Bank Report also told about the education and health services of this nation.
 - e) Cuba occupied infant mortality rate is lowest in some regions and longest life expectancies.
 - f) Highest share of its 13 percent of the national budget for the education sectors
 - g) 6 to 16 ages children are education is compulsory.
 - h) Students can be attended primary school for 6 years, then 3-4 years for basic secondary or high school.
 - i) After completed his or her basic secondary level, then education can categories into two types i) Pre-university education, ii) Technical or Professional training.
 - j) Technical schools and all universities are running by sector of the 'Ministry of Higher Education (MES). The MES has responsibilities for conducting all necessary steps for development like regulating teaching, implementing educational policies, managing the schools, methodology and courses and standard.
 - k) Mostly 400,000 numbers of Students have enrolled in a total of 47 universities.

Some universities are in Cuba

- The University of Havana
- Universidad Catolica de Santo Tomas de Villanueva
- Universidad Masonica Universidad de Oriente
- Universidad de La Salle en Nuevo Vedado
- Universidad de Oriente
- Universidad Central de Las Villas etc.

Three stages of the university education system

1st Stage – The Licenciatura (Bachelor's degree equivalent) or professional degree, if medicine degree then requires five to six years.

2nd stage– In the field of higher education

consists of three levels: Diploma, Maestria, and Especialista. Within every level, students are must be completed a minimum of 200 hours on theory and practicum, and internship.

3rd stage–higher education for Doctoral Degree. 3-45 years consider for complete his or her study.

Youth Policies: General Characterization

Irrespective of age, gender, caste, creed, ethnicity, religion economic status of the people, residence education should universal and free in all Cuban nations. State create funded for Educational policies and managed by the ministries.

There is some strategy for youth promotion and social inclusion through technical courses and vocational training and enhance or encourage positive social mobility.

University for All concept

The government will provide TV courses, which are lecturers on Cuban and Universal History, Philosophical concept, thought, Music, Ballet, Cinema, Drama, Dance, etc. in various languages like English, French, Italian and Portuguese.

Educational Television and Video screening rooms

Two national TV channels are broadcasts channel for the various programmewhich is related to the national teaching system, different kind of materials for primary, secondary schooling children, and Pre University lectures series, also technological and digital education, etc. and university entrance exams preparation.

Discussion

As part of the discussion, it's most important for any research of study, so the researcher can discuss the part of the beginning of the educational history of Cuban civilization. Early the 16th century to 1898 Cuba was colonized by Spain when the island was occupied by the United States. In 1727, the oldest university in Cuba is the University of Havana and is also the oldest in the American continent. The literacy rate was 36.1% to 42% in 1900. In a short period, Cuba's new government was changed the total educational system, 97% of Cubans ages belong from 15 to 24 were literate in the year 2000. Education is essential to every

government every nation. It's created for economic significance will be even better in the future.

Conclusion

In the last part of this researcher can conclude that point of view, before the Batista period was so negative effect on the Cuban society's people but after the era of Fidel Castro the educational concept will change rapidly but it not so easy. So researcher concludes at the time of beginning Marxist-Leninist ideology it is significant role after 5 decades of Marxist-Leninist ideology, who is firstly understanding and analyze need to work on schooling conditions independently and reform to educational setup for the Cuban peoples and particularly to Martí's educational thought has been a great role for reform new educational progress and educational policies. Every nation has positive and negative approaches in the different dimensions but we think more about social equality, social justice, social value, and awareness of everyone to own life as well as family.

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